

Heavy Metals Impact on Farmland Soil in Jabaka Mining Community, Zamfara State, Nigeria

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8249922

Abstract

Soil samples were collected from farm soil at the depth of 0-15cm from Jabaka (MSZ) mining Areas, Zamfara State. The level of soil contamination were assessed by Geo-accumulation Index (Igeo) and Pollution Load Index (PLI). The Geo-accumulation studies shows that the soil was moderately polluted by Pb(1.31mg/kg), Fe(0.95mg/kg) and Zn(1.41mg/kg). The Pollution Load Index result shows that farmland soil was polluted, with PLI value of 3.7 for Jabaka farm soil. Also, the geochemical distribution of the metals in the soil samples were revealed by sequential extraction procedures, 90% of the metal concentrations were found in the residual fractions. This shows that the high level of contamination of the farmland soil is associated to the mining activities going in the community.

Keywords: Jabaka, Geo-accumulation Index (Igeo), Pollution Load Index (PLI), Geo-chemical distribution, Zamfara State.

Received: March 2, 2023

Revised: March 15, 2023

Accepted: March 17, 2023

Cite this Paper as: O. Q. Sholadoye, T. A. Lawal and C. C. Onoyima, "Heavy Metals Impact on Farmland Soil in Jabaka Mining Community," *Science Journal of Applied and Natural Sciences*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 69-77, 2023.

About the Journal: SJANS is a multidisciplinary science journal and the official journal of the Faculty of Science, Nigeria Police Academy, Kano, Nigeria

1.0 Introduction

Nigeria is endowed with metallic and non- metallic mineral resources as well human resources capable of exploring these resources for industrial growth. But unfortunately what the country is facing today is that most of the mineral development, especially the exploration process is done by informal and in most cases illegal miners using very crude techniques with no consideration for the environment or human health. (Gyang and Ashano, 2010). These processes by artisanal miners greatly affects the environment largely due to the fact that most of the mining activities are carried out without appropriate technology and skills, and are reluctant to imbibe best practices in their operations. While the enormous Mineral deposits portray potentials for industrial and technological development, the manner in which the resources are exploited portrays great danger for the communities where the resources are found (Malomo, 2007). The present studies is aim at the assessing the level of soil pollution by some heavy metals in farmland soil of Jabaka gold mining community in Maru Area of Zamfara State.

2.0 Materials and Methods

In the preparation of reagents, all the glass wear used were thoroughly washed with detergent and rinsed several times with distilled water and oven dried. The chemicals used were analytical grade.

2.1 Study Area

The studied area was Jabaka community in Maru areas of Zamfara State and is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Map of Zamfara State showing the Study Area (Maru).

Table 1: Samples Identification and Coding for Soil Samples

S/No	Samples	Code
1	Maru Soil Sample Zamfara	MSZ
2	Zamfara Background Soil Sample	ZBS

2.2 Collection of Soil Samples

Soil samples were collected at the depth of 15cm. The soil samples were transferred into clean well labeled polythene bag containers. Each soil sample was collected from five sampling spot at 30cm equal distance from each other, and then mixed thoroughly to obtain a composite sample (Uduma, 2014). The samples were then transported to the laboratory for further treatment. The background samples were collected from mining free, unpolluted and conserved environments state such as biological garden in the state.

2.3 Sample Pretreatment

The wet samples were air dried under the room temperature in the laboratory. The samples were ground and sieved through 2 mm mesh sieve and stored in a clean and labeled plastic container for further analysis.

2.4 Digestion of Soil Samples

0.25g of the dried soil samples were weighed into platinum crucibles. The digestions were carried out by mixing 6cm³ of concentrated HNO₃, 4cm³ of concentrated HF and 2cm³ of 50% H₂O₂ solution. The digestion was carried out on a sand bath at a temperature of 200-230°C and the acid mixtures were evaporated to dryness. 20cm³ of 0.25M HNO₃ was added to dissolved the residue and warm for 10 minutes, filtered and transferred to 50cm³ plastic container and make up to 50cm³ volume with 0.25M HNO₃ Solution. The digested samples were subjected to Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer model Varian AA240FS for total metals determinations. (Cheng-Yung *et al.*, 2005). The following metals were determined Pb , Fe, Zn, Cu and Cd.

2.5 Sequential Extraction Procedures

A seven step sequential extraction procedures was used i.e water soluble fraction, exchangeable fraction, carbonate fraction, amorphous metal oxide, crystalline metal oxide, bound to organic matter fraction and residual fraction (Cheng-Yung *et al.*, 2005).

2.6 Pollution Load Index (PLI)

The pollution load index is obtained as the n-root from the n-CFs that is obtained for all the metals. The PLI is expressed by Adel *et al.*, 2011.

$$PLI = \sqrt[n]{CF1 \times CF2 \times CF3 \times CFn \dots} \quad 1$$

Where CF = contamination factors, n is the number of metals. The PLI values >1 indicates Polluted. PLI values of < 1 indicate no Pollution.

2.7 Geo-accumulation Index (Igeo)

Importance of geochemical base line natural and anthropogenic anomalies coexists in environmental geochemical research. All manmade chemical changes irrespective of their origin are addition to a natural background (Baize and Sterckeman, 2001). Geo- accumulation Index (Igeo) is used to estimate the degree of anthropogenic pollution in the soil. It is the enrichment on geological substrates and is calculated using equation (2).

$$Igeo = \log_2 C_n / 1.5 \times B_n \quad 2 \quad (\text{Forstner } et al., 1993)$$

Where C_n is the concentration of the examined metal in the soil.

B_n is the geochemical background concentration in soil and 1.5 is the correction factor for variation in background values due to lithogenic effect. Igeo consist of seven classes which are:

Igeo ≤ 0 Practically unpolluted, 1 < Igeo ≤ 1 Unpolluted to Moderately Polluted

2 < Igeo ≤ 3 Moderately Polluted, 3 < Igeo ≤ 4 Strongly Polluted

4 < Igeo ≤ 5 Strongly to very strongly Polluted, 5 < Igeo ≤ 6 Very strongly Polluted

3.0 Results and Discussion

Lead

The mean lead concentration in the soil samples ranges from 73.4 ± 0.14 – 413.2 ± 0.21 mg/kg. Samples ZBS had the concentration of 73.4 ± 0.14 mg/kg while sample MSZ had the concentration of 413.2 ± 0.21 mg/kg. Sample MSZ is obtained from farmland area which might be polluted as a result of activities of artisanal miners while Sample ZBS is obtained from mining free environment, hence the low lead concentration.

The distribution of lead in the fractions follows the trend, residual > metal oxide > organic > carbonate > exchangeable > water soluble fraction in all the samples. Water soluble and exchangeable fractions represent the most mobile and readily available metals (Zakir *et al.*, 2007). The result of exchangeable fractions was very low < 1% of the total fractions concentration in the present study. The exchangeable metal ions are those metal that are released readily into the environment, which are most available for plant uptake and organism and could be easily released by any alteration of ionic strength of the soil solution medium (Filguerias *et al.*, 2002). The low concentration of lead in some of the fractions in the soil is an indication of low risk of lead released into the environment also a low potential of food chain contamination in those areas.

Metal oxide fraction (crystalline metal oxide and amorphous metal oxide). The concentration of lead in these fractions ranged from 32.28 ± 0.004 to 35.092 ± 0.003 mg/kg for crystalline metal oxide while 0.68 ± 0.001 to 0.791 ± 0.001 mg/kg for Amorphous metal oxide.. The availability e.g. metals in this fraction depend in adsorption of the metals with the Fe-Mn mineral surface which depend on the soil redox state. Low percentage of lead in this fraction indicates a less reductive state in the samples. Metal associated with oxide minerals are likely to be released under reducing condition (Zakir *et al.*, 2008).

The concentration of lead in carbonate fractions ranges from 0.38 ± 0.03 to 16.82 ± 0.003 mg/kg. The Carbonate could be an alternative adsorbent for many metals when the metal oxides are less abundant (Stone and Dropp 1996). The metal bound to carbonate is sensitive to pH and is mobilizable when the pH value is low. Shaheen *et al.*, (2013) also reported > 18% of lead for carbonate fraction in German soil.

Lead concentration in organic fraction ranges from 8.28 ± 0.02 to 10.32 ± 0.007 mg/kg. Organic matter has high affinity for metal, forming stable complexes especially with divalent ion (Filguerias *et al.*, 2002). Metallic pollutant associated with organic fraction always remained in the soil for long period but after sometimes it may be demobilised by decomposition process (Kennedy *et al.*, 1997).

Lead concentrations in residual fractions ranges from 5573.1 ± 0.98 to 11103.5 ± 0.98 mg/kg. The residual fractions represent metal associated with silicate clay minerals (Halavay *et al.*, 2014). The relatively high percentage of the residual fractions in the soil samples indicate lithogenic origin of the metal contaminants. Residual fractions is a major carrier of metal in environmental system and the percentage of this fractions indicate the degree of non- availability of the metal to biota except over long period of time (Ma and Rao, 1997).

The result of geo accumulation index (Igeo) for the studied areas shows that the soil is moderately polluted by lead i.e 1.31 mg/kg (MSZ).

Table 2: Mean results for Total Metal Concentration of the Soil Samples.(mg/kg)

Samples	Pb	Fe	Zn	Cu	Cd
MSZ	413.2±0.21	62182±0.35	982.8±0.49	ND	ND
ZBS	73.4±0.14	72924±0.64	89.6±0.141	45.0±0.01	ND

ND = Not Detected

Table 3: Mean Lead Concentrations in the fractions (mg/kg)

Fractions	MSZ	ZBS
Amorphous	0.688±0.001	0.791±0.001
Crystalline	35.092±0.003	32.815±0.007
Water soluble	0.064±0.001	0.095±0.001
Exchangeable	0.103±0.001	0.1405±0.002
Organic	10.32±0.007	8.27±0.021
Carbonate	16.819±0.003	0.376±0.003
Residual	5573.1±0.98	11103.5±0.98

Table 4: Mean iron concentrations in the fractions (mg/kg)

Fractions	MSZ	ZBS
Amorphous	114.95±0.02	102.96±0.04
Crystalline	46.612±0.002	33.172±0.003
Water soluble	ND	0.729±0.001
Exchangeable	0.052±0.003	0.079±0.00
Organic	180.92±0.51	126.75±0.064
Carbonate	0.11±0.0014	0.0345±0.001
Residual	25409±1.141	17272.5±3.55

ND = below detection limit

Table 5: Mean zinc concentrations in the fractions (mg/kg)

Fractions	MSZ	ZBS
Amorphous	2.47±0.06	1.792±0.005
Crystalline	0.0245±0.002	0.261±0.0014
Water soluble	ND	ND
Exchangeable	0.124±0.003	0.114±0.0003
Organic	0.581±0.001	1.326±0.002
Carbonate	0.395±0.0014	0.759±0.0014
Residual	13.01±0.014	56.50±0.14

ND = below detection limit

Table 6: Mean copper concentrations in the fractions (mg/kg)

Fractions	MSZ	ZBS
Amorphous	ND	ND
Crystalline	ND	ND
Water soluble	ND	ND
Exchangeable	ND	ND
Organic	ND	ND
Carbonate	ND	ND
Residual	ND	ND

ND = below detection limit

Iron

The mean iron concentration in the soil samples ranges from 62182 ± 0.35 – 72924 ± 0.64 mg/kg. Samples ZBS had the higher concentration while sample MSZ had the lower concentration of iron in the samples. The sequential extraction studies revealed the distribution pattern of iron in the fractions. The trends follow thus, residual > metal oxide > organic > carbonate > exchangeable > water soluble fraction in all the samples. The concentration of Fe ranges from not detected to 0.729 ± 0.001 mg/kg (ZBS) in water soluble fraction and from 0.052 ± 0.003 to 0.079 ± 0.00 mg/kg in exchangeable fraction. The low proportion of iron in this fraction implies less availability of iron to biota and environment.

Iron concentration in carbonate and organic fractions is presented in Table 3. The percentage of iron in the fractions is 0.00041% and 0.0063% respectively. The result agreed with Tianhung *et al.*, (1998) which also reported a low iron content in both carbonate and organic fraction respectively.

The concentrations of iron in crystalline and amorphous metal oxide were presented in Table 4. The percentage of iron in each fraction was 0.51% for amorphous metal oxide and 0.18% for crystalline metal oxide. The concentration of iron in this fraction is higher than concentrations of iron in other fractions except in residual fraction with about 98.70% and this shows that the non-availability of the metal for plant up take and its association with primary minerals which can only be released to the environment over long period of time. The result of geo accumulation index (Igeo) for the studied area shows that the farmland soil was unpolluted to moderately polluted by iron i.e 0.95mg/kg (MSZ).

Zinc

The mean concentration of zinc in the samples ranges from 89.6 ± 0.14 – 982.8 ± 0.49 mg/kg. Sample ZBS had the least concentration while sample MSZ had the highest concentration. The distribution pattern of zinc in the soil fraction follows this trend, residual > metal oxide > carbonate > organic > exchangeable > water soluble fraction in all the samples. The concentrations of zinc in water soluble were below detection limits while that of exchangeable fractions ranges from 0.114 ± 0.0003 - 0.124 ± 0.003 mg/kg in the samples. The percentage of zinc in both fractions is <1% of the total zinc concentration in the soil fractions. The low concentration may be as a result of zinc association with primary minerals which indicate less zinc pollution in the farmland soil.

The zinc concentration in carbonate fraction ranges from 0.395 ± 0.0014 mg/kg (MSZ) to 0.759 ± 0.0014 mg/kg (ZBS) while concentration in organic fraction ranges from 0.581 ± 0.001 mg/kg (MSZ) to 1.326 ± 0.002 mg/kg (ZBS). The percentage of zinc in both carbonate and organic fractions was 1.49% and 2.47% respectively. Carbonate tends to be major adsorbent for many metals when there is reduction in metal oxide and organic matter (Okoro *et al.*, 2012). This means when there is high concentration of metal associated with metal oxide and organic fractions, the concentration of such metal with carbonate fraction will be less. Vinod *et al.*, (2013) also reported low zinc concentration in both carbonate and organic fractions.

The metal oxide fraction was found to be 5.59% of the total zinc concentration in the soil. The association of zinc with Fe-Mn oxides fractions shows the high stability constant behaviour of zinc oxide (Ma and Rao, 1997). Metal bound to metal oxide is available under reducing condition. The reducing condition enhance desorption of metals held unto the fraction due to reductive dissolution of iron and manganese oxide (Dung and Ma, 2004). However, the concentration of zinc in residual fraction was found to be higher about 90.13% of total zinc in the soil. Higher proportion of residual zinc indicates non- availability of the metal for plant up-take. This could be traced to lithogenic

origin of the metal in the farmland soil of the studied areas. Shaheem *et al.*, (2013) reported high concentration of zinc in the residual fraction in their study of Egyptian soil.

Table 7: Mean cadmium concentrations in the fractions (mg/kg)

Fractions	MSZ	ZBS
Amorphous	0.317±0.002	ND
Crystalline	ND	ND
Water soluble	ND	ND
Exchangeable	ND	ND
Organic	ND	ND
Carbonate	ND	0.0055±0.001
Residual	ND	ND

ND : below detection limit

Table 7: Contamination factor (Cf) mg/kg in the different sites

Samples	Pb	Fe	Cd	Zn	Cu
MSZ	5.63	0.85	0.00	10.97	ND

ND = below detection limit

Table 8: Geo-accumulation Index (Igeo) mg/kg in different sites

Samples	Pb	Fe	Cd	Zn	Cu
MSZ	1.31	0.95	ND	1.41	ND

ND = below detection limits

Table 9: Pollution Load Index (PLI) mg/kg

Samples	PLI
MSZ	3.7

Copper

The mean concentration of copper in the soil samples were presented in Table 2. The concentration of copper was below detection limits in sample MSZ while the concentration was found to be 45.0±0.01 in sample ZBS. The sequential extraction studied revealed that copper was below detection limits in all the fractions. The low concentration of copper in exchangeable fraction and water soluble fraction might be attributed to association of copper with primary minerals. Also, copper form strong complexes with ligands (Bika, 1994). In the absence of reactive soil components especially iron oxides, copper is complex with organic matter like the total copper concentration in most soil samples are generally low which means copper is expected to be bioavailable. The result of geo accumulation index (Igeo) shows that the farmland soil of the studied area is unpolluted by copper.

Cadmium

The mean concentrations of cadmium in the studied areas were below the detection limit in all the samples. The result of sequential extraction also revealed that cadmium was only determined in two fractions. The concentration was found to be 0.317±0.002 mg/kg in amorphous metal oxide and 0.0055±0.001mg/kg in carbonate fraction in samples MSZ and BSZ respectively. The low concentration in non-residual and residual fractions is an indication of non-availability of the metal

in the environment or the biota and poses no threat. Also, the result of geo accumulation index (Igeo) shows that the farmland soil of the studied area is unpolluted by cadmium.

However, the pollution load index (PLI) as shown in Table 9, for the studied area shows that the farmland soil is heavily polluted, with PLI value of 3.1.

Conclusion

The results of the metals concentrations in the farmland soil of the studied areas were examined with different indices such as Geo- accumulation index, Contamination factor and Pollution load index. The result shows the level of pollution ranges from low contamination to high contamination and low pollution to moderate pollution load index. Also, the behaviour of metal in soil was studied by sequential extraction method, which revealed that metals were not bio-available about 90% of the studied metals were associated with residual fractions which implies most of these metals naturally are not available. The pollution of the farmland of the studied areas is as result of anthropogenic activities going on the environment such as mining activities.

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